

Research Software Engineering: A SWEBOK Specialism?

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Abstract—The Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK) V4.0 was released in October 2024, introducing new topics to enhance foundational knowledge in software engineering, updating existing knowledge areas, and retiring outdated subjects. It aims to better align related disciplines by reorganising and renaming content within different knowledge areas. Established in 2012, the field of research software engineering has grown rapidly as a movement in many countries. However, there is currently an insufficient transfer of state-of-the-art knowledge from software engineering to research software engineering and domain researchers, and vice versa, in part, leading to an incomplete understanding in software engineering of the domain-specific and general challenges in research software engineering. In this extended abstract, we imagine an alternative SWEBOK where this 12-year history of research software and over 10,000 research software engineers were included.

I. RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

Computational and data science and engineering, which are dependent on research software, ranging from small scripts for data analysis to large codes for modelling and simulation [1], are revolutionising advances throughout science and society [2]. *Research software* is software that was created during the research process or for a research purpose in support of research in any scholarly discipline [3]. It differs from traditional software in many ways, e.g., the complexity of the underlying domain, the uncertainty of the outcomes of the research process, and the type of stakeholders involved. Research software has been developed by domain experts and end-user developers who have a limited understanding, if any, of fundamental software engineering concepts such as abstraction, encapsulation, modularity, cohesion, coupling, and separation of concerns or the application of software design principles such as SOLID¹. While the 10,000+ worldwide RSEs in academia, laboratories, and industry have more software engineering knowledge and are increasingly involved in research software projects, research software still has not reached a level of maturity compared with the conventional

¹A set of principles proposed by Martin [4] that guide the design of software to make it more understandable, maintainable, reusable, and extensible.

tools of empirical and theoretical science, and it is unclear how the SWEBOK can be leveraged by the research software engineering (RSEng) community [5].

II. AN ALTERNATIVE SWEBOK

If RSEng had been part of the SWEBOK v4.0 process, we imagine additions or changes in many knowledge areas (KAs) flowing from its unique characteristics. Specifically, the uncertainty and complexity of research software requires iteration on requirements, architecture, design, construction, and testing. Testing and QA are also complicated by frequent lack of knowable outcomes. RSEng is often done collaboratively between RSEs and researchers, many of whom have hands-on involvement in the software. SE management and professional practice also would change to reflect RSEs groups and societies, working primarily in the context and with the incentives of scholarly research rather than software or business. Similarly, much RSEng works on experimental computers, leading to changes in computing and mathematical foundations. Overall, the changes that might occur would be similar to those driven by Agile and DevOps in SWEBOK v4.0, impacting most KAs, but likely not requiring new KAs.

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